

Small bowel angiodysplasia in elderly – A rare and incidental finding but most common cause of small bowel bleed.

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- **Abstract: INTRODUCTION:** Angiodysplasia is the most frequent etiology of small bowel bleeding or formerly called obscure gastrointestinal bleeding (OGIB) especially in patients of older age. Angiodysplasia is an abnormal, tortuous, dilated small blood vessel in the mucosal and submucosal layers of the GI tract. A 75 years old male patient presented to a tertiary care centre, a known case of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease of lung for 16 years with chief complaint of easy fatigability and generalised body weakness for one year and intermittent history of black color stool for approximately 14 months.
- **METHODS:** Initial diagnostic tools used were Upper GI endoscopy and colonoscopy for our patient but remained undiagnosed. So further investigated for capsule endoscopy and diagnosed with small bowel angiodysplasia. Other investigations done were complete blood count, stool routine micro for occult blood. **RESULTS:** At present patient does not have active bleed so patient was treated conservatively with Tablet Thalidomide (50mg) two times a day and iron supplements.
- **CONCLUSION:** Small bowel angiodysplasia is a rare but most common cause of small bowel bleed in elderly population. Various medical, ablative and surgical options are available but recently thalidomide has shown better efficacy to prevent angiodysplasia bleed.

INTRODUCTION

Small bowel angiodysplasia (SBD) is the most common vascular abnormality in GI tract which causes melena. It is diagnosed by GI scopy and angiography and histopathological examination [1]. Angiodysplasia is an abnormal, tortuous, dilated small blood vessel in the mucosal and submucosal layers of the GI tract. The abnormal vessels consists of endothelium with scant or no smooth muscle [2]. Angiodysplasia is the most frequent etiology of small bowel bleeding or formerly called obscure gastrointestinal bleeding (OGIB) in patients more than 60 years of age [3]. Angiodysplasia is not related to any hereditary, skin, or systemic disease and can affect any part of the GI tract.[4]

CASE REPORT

A 75 years old male patient presented to a tertiary care centre, a known case of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease of lung for 16 years with chief complaint of easy fatigability and generalised body weakness for one year and intermittent history of black color stool for approximately 14 months. There was no history of NSAIDS, antiplatelet or any surgery. On presentation patient was afebrile, heart rate was 96 beats/min, blood pressure was 108/70mmhg and oxygen saturation was 96% on room air. On general examination, pallor and koilonachyia were present and systemic examination was insignificant.

On laboratory tesings, complete blood count shows haemoglobin 7.5 grams%, WBC 6000/cumm, platelet counts 2.91 lakh/cumm, PCV 22.33%, MCV 57%, MCH 21.79pg, MCHC 38.06%, Stool routine micro was positive for occult blood. Table 1 shows serial haemoglobin drop from 11.8gm% to 7.5gm% and stool occult blood positive.

Table 1 – Serial monitoring of Complete blood count and stool occult blood

Date	Hb	PCV	MCV	MCH	MCHC	Stool routine micro for occult blood
15/07/2020						Positive
15/08/2020	11.8gm%					Weakly positive
18/01/2021	8.1gm%	25.38	64	20.40	31.91	
19/01/2021						Positive
16/04/2021	12.1gm%	37.1	82.26	26.83	32.61	Positive
9/03/2023	7.7gm%	23.13	56	18.73	33.29	
8/05/2023	6.8gm%	19.47	56	19.42	34.92	Positive
24/11/2023	8.5gm%	23.53	62	22.25	36.12	
21/12/2023	7.5gm%	22.33	57	21.79	38.06	

In view of chronic microcytic anemia with positive stool occult blood, patient was advised for upper GI and colonoscopy which was not showing any evidence of stigmata of bleed. So small bowel bleed was suspected and capsule endoscopy was performed. Capsule endoscopy shows small bowel angiodysplasias (Figure 1). At present patient does not have active bleed so patient was treated conservatively with Tablet Thalidomide (50mg) two times a day and iron supplements. We have planned to do APC if there is active bleed from angiodysplasia.

Figure 1 – Mid and distal jejunum angiodysplasia without active bleed

DISCUSSION

Our patient had small bowel angiodysplasia which has incidence of 5% but is the most common cause of GI bleed in elderly population. Because angiodysplasia is omnipresent throughout the GI tract, a combination of routine blood investigations with endoscopy is necessary.

Upper GI endoscopy and colonoscopy are common initial diagnostic tools.

Angiodysplasia on direct visualization from endoscopy or colonoscopy looks like 5 to 10 mm flat cherry-red fern-like projecting vessels originating from a central artery.

Small bowel angiodysplasia may require further evaluation with wireless video capsule endoscopy or deep bowel enteroscopy if the initial workup is negative.

Radionuclide scanning images are the most sensitive radiologic diagnostic tool during active bleeding, which can detect bleeding up to 0.1 to 0.5 ml/min.

Helical CT angiography and magnetic resonance angiography are also useful investigative tools to investigate further. Angiography is usually necessary for actively bleeding hemodynamically unstable patients or patients in whom the active source of bleeding remains unidentified with conventional diagnostic methods which also provides the benefit of therapeutic intervention at the same time.

Treatment Options

Angiodysplasia is an incidental finding in endoscopy and it is divided into incidental angiodysplasia, nonbleeding angiodysplasia and an actively bleeding angiodysplasia in a patient with GI bleeding.

Treatment is decided by these factors.

Incidental angiodysplasia- if no history of GI bleeding or unexplained iron deficiency anemia; Incidental angiodysplasia should not be treated. The future risk of bleeding is unknown, and the recommendation is based solely on expert opinions.

Nonbleeding angiodysplasia in a patient with GI bleeding - In these patients, angiodysplasia should have treatment, which again has its basis on expert opinions.

Actively bleeding angiodysplasia- When it comes to treating most patients, the same protocol that is used to treat upper and lower gastrointestinal bleeding, hemodynamic resuscitation, frequent monitoring of the complete blood count, and blood transfusion if necessary. The state of hemodynamic stability and the presence or absence of current bleeding should be taken into consideration while making treatment options.

Endoscopy or colonoscopy - Endoscopy or colonoscopy: If angiodysplasia is detected during an endoscopy or colonoscopy, the following methods can be employed to treat it:

Argon plasma coagulation ablation, electrocoagulation, endoscopic clips and band ligation, injection sclerotherapy.

Angiography done in patients with active bleeding who have failed in above mentioned treatment, and poor surgical candidates. It is done with temporary absorbable gelatin sponge, local infusion of vasopressin or embolization with micro-coils.

Surgery - Surgical resection is required eventually in patients with heavy active bleeding requiring multiple blood unit transfusion with failed all other measures described above[5]

Angiogenesis inhibitors - Thalidomide and bevacizumab have been described with success in the treatment of gastrointestinal vascular malformation, including angiodysplasia.[6][7][8] In one clinical trial, an effective response rate, which was described GI bleeding cessation by over 50% by the end of the year, was 71.6% in the thalidomide treated group compared to the control group 3.7%.[9] Thalidomide use requires some caution because of teratogenic effects. Another angiogenesis inhibitor bevacizumab is a human monoclonal antibody against vascular endothelial growth factor and has been used in some case reports and series for the treatment of refractory GI bleeding related to angiodysplasia but because of the paucity of data should be used as last resort.[8]

Hormone therapy – treatment with estrogen with or without progesterone didn't show any benefit in prevention of bleeding in angiodysplasia[10][11]

Octreotide – It is effective in refractory angiodysplasia related GI bleeding with twice daily subcutaneous injection with dose of 50 to 100 mcg and long acting form octreotide-LAR given intramuscularly once a month. The studies which evaluated octreotide showed 73 to 76% of patients showed response in terms of bleeding events, transfusion requirement, and mean hemoglobin.[12] [13][14][15] Based on the results of these studies, octreotide may be an option in patients with refractory angiodysplasia-related bleeding.

Differential diagnosis

Symptomatic angiodysplasia usually presents with symptoms similar to upper and lower GI bleeding, which is either unexplained iron deficiency anemia or GI bleeding. Differential diagnosis includes common causes of both upper and lower GI bleeding.

- Peptic ulcer disease
- Diverticulosis
- Colitis (ischemic, inflammatory bowel disease and radiation-induced, infectious)
- Hemorrhoidal bleeding
- GI malignancies, such as colon and rectal cancer.[16]

Prognosis

Patients with angiodysplasia have a good prognosis because the bleeding subsides automatically in most cases. Patients with ten or more angiodysplasia lesions or lesions larger than 10 mm, may have a worse prognosis, lower hemoglobin level, and require more blood transfusions.[17]

CONCLUSION

Small bowel angiodysplasia is a rare but most common cause of small bowel bleed in elderly population. Various medical , ablative and surgical options are available but recently thalidomide has shown better efficacy to prevent angiodysplasia bleed.

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